

***HINDI BULAG ANG PUSO: THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF WEDDED
TO VISUALLY IMPAIRED PARTNERS***

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Hindi Bulag ang Puso: The Lived Experiences of Wedded to Visually Impaired Partners

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Abstract

This research looked into the lived experiences of individuals wedded to visually impaired partners. This study employed face-to-face interview using a semi-structured questionnaires as an interview guide flow. This research employed a phenomenological approach where thematic analysis was utilized, and responses were qualitatively evaluated as means for developing subthemes, and superordinate themes. With this type of data analysis, the researchers were able to identify common patterns that provide significant answers to the research questions addressed in the study. Results presented eight (8) dominant themes centering on the participants, namely; (1) Life of a Dim Sighted Individual, (2) Foundation of Love Ideation, (3) Walk down the Lover's Lane, (4) Road to be Missus, (5) Art of living the Married Life, (6) Love in the Reflection of Two People, (7) Envisioning Future with Clear Sight, and (8) Valuable Lessons from Life Experience. Findings shows that compassion, acceptance, and love are a momentous decree in sustaining marriage relationships. In light of the findings, programs that can be establish is an optical/medical mission for at least during every quarter in order to lessen the financial burden of check ups for individuals with visual impairment with the support of Local Government Units (LGUs).

Keywords: *marriage, visual impairment, lived experiences, unconditional love*

Introduction

The inability to see might be a big deal, but it is a big deal that an individual with impairment must be able to confront to continue to live on. It is vital to recognize the potential opportunities that may be missed, even during challenging times. After the storm, the silver lining in the cloud will shine, even if eyes can barely see it (Lucksameepong & Kongka, 2024).

Visual impairment is one of the untold taxing phenomena in an individual's life. The stumbling block of visual impairment can contribute to social isolation. Adults with visual impairment experience lower rates of employment and increased rates of developing depression and anxiety (WHO, 2023). It is a significant obstacle in an individual's life and can occur when any part of the optical system is defective, diseased, or malfunctioned. It refers to a kind of vision loss, whether partial, total, or acquired (Pandey, 2018; Salvin, 2016).

In the Philippines, visual impairment remains a pressing public health concern that older adults with visual impairment exacerbates a high risk of discrimination (Jackson et al., 2019) and a trammel of attitudinal and access barriers in employment inclusion (Chhabra, 2020). Dealing with visual impairment is a hitherto challenge, and the lack of emotional support, limited accessibility to activities, as well as information, societal stigma, and other factors that exclude and isolate visually impaired individuals from anyone else signify struggles (Envision, 2024).

Additionally, individuals with visual impairment may experience difficulties participating in community interaction, engaging in social activities, and engaging in society. According to Indrayani & Immanuel (2022), these difficulties can lead to exclusion, as individuals with visual impairments may develop feelings of inadequacy, perceive themselves as inferior, experience reduced self-efficacy, and may implicate depression in their daily lives.

Nevertheless, marriage is associated with visual impairment hereinafter marriage unites partners socially, and economically this accords with certain agreed-upon rights that are bestowed to them (Suadi & Jamayah, 2019). In the perspective of Christianity, marriage is a formal union between a man and a woman- a covenant and a sacred promise between individuals bound by love, faith, hope, and dreams. The union constitutes three basic elements including the ability of both parties to marry each other, parties shall have consent mutually, and a legally bind contract by the law as required (Aliano, 2018; Abodunrin & Akinsola, 2019; Stritof & Blomquist, 2023). In the Filipino setting, it is not just the most awaited events but also the most important decisions as this commitment remains until death do them apart based upon the vows and honor of one another thus remains as a valued goal for most individuals.

In defiance of, when phenomena arise such as visual impairment difficulties it could ensue day-to-day life and the challenges may increase substantially between the marital relationship. These might negatively affect their partner's well being, functioning, social involvement, and the quality of their marriage. For disabled individuals, it may seem hard for them to find a partner as this may compel stigma, and strict public judgements from the society which include hurdles in pursuit of love, and companionship. Conversely, the challenge lies in navigating, and finding love in a predominantly visual world as the disability of an individual may hinder them from performing personal, and daily chores without the help and support of a partner. At its core, marriage embodies the intertwining commitment to love, partnership, development, and growth. Nevertheless, views have generated immense challenges for marital relationships between individuals with normal vision married to a visually impaired partner.

Moreover, in recent statistics- Bourne et al. (2020) concluded that among 7.79 billion people, an estimated 49.1 million people were

diagnosed with visual impairment and blindness as of 2020. In the Philippines, the prevalence of visual impairment is 1.98% thus cataract is one of the main causes of visual impairment (Cubillan, 2018), and upon the statistics of Philippine National Blindness and Eye Disease in 2018 the prevalence equates to 1.11 million Filipinos affected with cataract, 400,000 with uncorrected refractive errors, nearly 300,000 with glaucoma, and 200,000 with maculopathy. Henceforth, over 4 million Filipinos live with undiagnosed eye conditions that require attention (Garcia et al., 2021). Hence, visual impairment can also be caused by a catastrophic accident, this includes injuries to the head, face, inflammation, and bruise (Eisenberg et al., 2023), this insinuate that visual impairment is one of the social phenomena that Filipinos experience.

With regards to marriage, in 2023 the Philippine Statistic Authority (PSA) reported that the total figure of marriage is increasing from 356,839 in the year 2021 and marked a 25.9 percent bump up in 2022 which equates to 449,428 registered marriages. The uncertainty of the dimension of marriage journey to a visually impaired partner seems to be a crucial part of their daily lives. This complexity gives rise to questions such as, what are the experiences and married life of wedded to visually impaired partner.

Despite studies throughout the years, there remains lack of research on issues and challenges that have been and still faced by visually impaired couples that is why the researchers pursued the study “Hindi Bulag ang Puso: The Lived Experiences of Wedded to Visually Impaired Partner” or in an English locution “The Heart is not Blind” to understand the marriage journey of individuals wedded to the visually impaired partners on how their love emerged before, and up until the present day.

Research Questions

The researchers of the study aimed to explore the lived experiences of wedded to visually impaired partners. By understanding this specific group, the study intends to provide insights that are relevant to both the university, the broader community, and the local government as well. Specifically, this study endeavored to achieved the following research questions:

1. How do individuals experience life while being wedded to visually impaired partners?
2. What program may be designed based on the results of the study?

Literature Review

A study of Kwon and Park (2019) entitled “A narrative study on the experiences of facing and coping the crisis in the wives of men having visual impairment revealed that wives of visually impaired partners faced a variety of challenges encompassing emotional distress including despair, role changes and it is evidently accepted as an economic burden, and crisis of their family. Thus, coping strategies are being motivated by compassion and respect towards their husbands, maternal affection for their children, as well as a sense of responsibility for their families endeavoring happiness, and trying to overcome the crisis by thinking positively. The study suggests that social supports are needed and that a certain amount should be given to the families who have fallen into the underprivileged class where the support is in need including counseling programs or self-help groups in the community as well as to provide a family education, treatment program for disabled individuals to help them recover- a need for support.

It is upsetting that visual impairment disrupts the social engagement of partners in a day-to-day activities. As stated by study of Bertrand et al., (2022) entitled “When one partner can no longer see: Exploring the lived experiences of romantic partner in the context of vision loss”, that due to major vision loss of an individual it ensue changes in everyday habits, routines, and activities thus also strike adjustment, and adaptations for their partners. The study then revealed that maintaining a couple's wellness in a time of disruption requires both effort from shared activities that may be lost, prioritized, or either be reshaped. Therefore, suggested that support systems for couples can be formulated to navigate the transitions of everyday activities. Furthermore, in relation to this, the study of Kathleen (2012) entitled “Vision impairment and blindness” similarly revealed that in doing daily chores, and social activities visually impaired partner cannot continue living without the help of their partners, special support, and care that causes limitations, psychological, and social pressures for the individual with visual impairment as well as his/her partner, and their child as well.

In addition, Suaidi and Jamayah (2019), in their study “Marital Satisfaction of Visually Impaired Couples,” divulged that visually impaired couples faced challenges in terms of child custody, communication, over and beyond social pressures that constitute to earn a living. It is revealed that child custody was a challenge for the visually impaired as their family does not put trust in them, followed by challenges in communication as non-verbal cues are important because it helps couples to have a better communication. The study recommended that individual wedded to visually impaired must reflect on hopes, and dreams for the future it shows that couples dreamt to build a home, a long-lasting married life, and with regards to welfare it is evidently that love is bound by support, tolerance, trust, and respect.

Methodology

Research Design

The main strategy employed in this study is qualitative approach. It was used to ascertain the lived experiences of individuals wedded to visually impaired partners. It looked over the story of other people by allowing them to unveil and hear their unnoticeable voices. Qualitative was chosen as it is the most suitable for the study to feature the ideas, opinions, and the experiences of the participants to uncover what is beyond the phenomena (Ugwu & Eze, 2023). The present data includes an in-depth data collection to understand the

specific event. The researcher's utilized phenomenological approaches where it is referred to as addressing topics across the full spectrum of humanities (Wertz,2023). Phenomenological approach was chosen to deeply understand the unique personal and communal experiences of the respondents focusing on the different perspectives which the subjects perceived, determined by their beliefs, and experiences as individuals wedded to visually impaired partners.

Participants

Individuals wedded to visually impaired partners were selected through the used of chain referrals "snowball sampling" to access specific groups of people that is difficult to access by means of asking peers, friends colleagues, and relatives (Naderifar et al., 2017). The study was conducted within the confines of the Province of Batangas, Philippines. Criterion may include but not limited to ages 28-55 years old as of March 2024, at least one of the couple has visually impaired either mild blindness, totally blind caused by glaucoma, cataract, uncorrected refractive errors, maculopathy or caused by catastrophic accidents. Due to limited access and as the study aim to understand lived experiences, a total of 2 respondents voluntarily consented to participate in the study. The researchers firmly believed that the 2 participants had been sufficient to illustrate the lived experiences of an individuals wedded to visually impaired partner.

Instruments

The researchers used semi-structured interviews to ensure that the study will be credible. The semi-structured were employed as the data gathering instrument in order to extract the personal experiences of the individuals wedded to visually impaired partners. The questionnaire designed for this study had been subjected to a validation process. As the researchers employed and used a semi-structured interview, the questionnaires were reviewed and evaluated.

Here, the researchers request feedback from the research adviser regarding the accuracy, relevance, and comprehensiveness of the questions and then collate the feedback and make necessary revisions to the guide questions based on the inputs received. Moreover, the questionnaires were typed and translated into Filipino and the translations were also validated to certify that the same meaning from English to Filipino are conveyed with the same meanings.

Procedure

The data collection undergoes a series of activities. The proponents puts a lot of time and effort in developing questions for the semi-structured interview. Nevertheless, the interview guide includes carefully constructed questions that covers the feelings, thoughts, and behaviors of the participants through the course of their experiences. The interview guide had been prepared by collecting important concepts from several articles and literature relating to the phenomenon therefore arranged the questions chronologically based from the general ones to the most specific types of questions consisting sixteen (16) grand questions along with one hundred and eighty-one (181) probes.

The researcher's personally administered the interview that takes place for 45 days/ a month, and two weeks in total which takes place from the last week of March 2024 to the first week of April 2024. During the 45 days, the proponents visit the participant five times to visit, and interview with 9 day intervals. This research is conducted through face-to-face interviews. The interview takes one (1) and a half hour (30 minutes) to complete. In analyzing the collected data's, the researchers brings the concept of thematic analysis. Thematic analysis requires interpretation in the process of selecting codes and constructing themes (Liwanag, 2023). With the use of thematic approach in analyzing the data's it helps to provide a clearer ideas of patterns that bolster the understanding relating to the participant's experiences and perspectives.

Ethical Considerations

As part of the confidentiality and anonymity of the data the researchers identifies several ethical considerations and it involves communicating the nature, intent and potential benefits of the study to participants. Kang et al., (2023) divulged that ensuring confidentiality encompasses an assurance that the personal information or data of the participants will be kept with integrity upholding the research ethical standards.

The researchers ensure that the participants voluntarily participate and have the willingness to take part in the study hence that their information will remain confidential. Each participant had been allowed to refuse, or otherwise decline and stop the interview at any time after the interview began if their safety is compromised thus participants can ask for their data to be removed from the records, or otherwise destroyed. Nevertheless, a safe place to interview had been chosen to create a secure environment where participants can freely express themselves, and tell their experiences without judgment.

This ethical considerations was carried out based on the compliance with the Republic Act 10173- Data Privacy Act of 2012 were data and information that will be gathered is not disclosed without their permission (Ople, 2024).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the discussion of results based on the lived experiences of individuals wedded to visually impaired partners. Nonetheless, this study does not reflect all individuals wedded to visually impaired partners as a whole, rather this is only a

representation of experiences. There were eight (8) superordinate themes that mainly focusses on the individual life experiences while being wedded to visually impaired partners. The themes are as follows; (see table 1 below)

Table 1. *Superordinate Themes and subthemes*

SUPERORDINATE THEMES	SUBTHEMES
Life of a Dim Sighted Individuals	The Starting Point of Vanishing Vision
Foundation of Love Ideation	Battles of Visually Impaired
Walk Down the Lover's Lane	Indelible Recollection of Parents
	Surviving in the Brink of Poverty
	Courting Bliss
	Dating Adventure of Teenagers
	Evolution of Relationships
Road to be Missus	Disobedience to Parents' Rules Leading to Marriage
	Cries of Disapproval from Family Members
Art of Living the Marriage Life	Changes in Horizon of Marriage
	Indulgement to Vices Resulting to Discourse
	Conquering Marriage Warmth
Love in the Reflection of Two People	Unleashing Affection's Warmth
	Supporting Partner Through Thick and Thin
Envisioning Future with Clear Sight	Breath of Relief from All Hard Work
	Whispers of Desires for Family's Future
	Relieving Vows Fifty Years Later
Valuable Lessons from Life Experiences	Life's Could Have Been
	Depths of Faith
	Married Couple Know-Hows on Relation Longevity

Life of a Dim Sighted Individual

This theme explored the reason of acquisition. It is highlighted that genetic rooted, and accident derived is the reason of their partner's impairment. Secondly, it emphasized the restrictions it brings, leads to exclusion, restrictions in day to day activities, and put reluctance to trust their partner in terms of business and livelihood [Interview Excerpt 1].

In accordance, this is analogous to which Eisenberg et al., (2023) confirmed that catastrophic accident can also result in visual impairment. Additionally, Stritof & Blomquist (2023), claims that visual impairment could have detrimental implications on the functioning, well-being, social life, marriage quality, and problems in day-to-day may arise.

Foundation of Love Ideation

The succeeding sub theme detailed the concept of love. First, it shows that strength comes from overcoming painful personal anecdotes such as desertion, and abandonment rooted from the father's negligence. Secondly, it can be said that familial matters including poverty, shape the idea of love, often times driving the sense of urgency to be wedded as a desire to break the cycle of poverty [Interview Excerpt 2].

Concomitantly, Jamison & Lo (2020) divulged that family structures can affect romantic outcomes as there is a link between parent and child. Hence, as mentioned by the factors of Stock et al., (2014) that poverty can have both cause and effect on relationship difficulty and relationship quality may suffer as a result of poverty stress.

Walk Down the Lover's Lane

This theme illustrated that courtship in the culture of Filipinos lies within a man's effort of paving a visit to woman's house, and sending love letters (stationary) to gain affection. Their courtship resembled to a game of hide and seek, retreating into the shadows during suitor visits. "Tukso" (teasing) had a significant role in developing their relationship. Additionally, respondents shared that their loved grows tremendously, leading them to conceal their love, and impulsively eloped (tanang) [Interview Excerpt 3].

This theme parallels to the affirmation of De Vera (2024); Regala et al., (2021), the traditional courtship in Philippines, anchored by Dr. Jose Rizal's penchant of writing, involves love letter as a courting style and rooted in cultural respect and sincerity through visiting house. Additionally, Carnahan & Anderson (2015), stated that attractiveness assessments can be impacted by peers. Thus, Khan et al., (2021) believed that an individual deviates from societal norms might risk a disadvantageous position when it comes to marriage where eloping are one of its categories.

Road to be Missus

This theme entails the road to intertwining commitment whereas the decision to be marry was prompted by father's violence upon discovering their dating. It was shown that an abrupt leap of transition occurred from being adolescent to wedded. It is revealed that

prior towards matrimony, their relationship was tampered with premarital sex. Forbye, criticism had been thrown and disapproval to marry a visually impaired partner [Interview Excerpt 4].

Based on the theme, this mirrors the Filipinos' conservative ways of dating, Rometic (2021), stated that failure to inform parents for a trip with lover can inflict violence and rumors. Thus, penetrative vaginal sex between couples prior to a formal marriage can put risk for both purposeful and unintentional harm (Behulu et al., 2019). Correspondingly, criticism and disagreement is a common problem encountered by wedded couple and may arise even from closely related individuals (Rusnak, 2024).

Art of Living the Married Life

Another theme that come to light lay bare that changes is inevitable. First, respondents discussed conflicts between personal desires and partnership, hampered with compliance (against will), including silently crying during intercourse, implying a lack of romantic feeling. Secondly, vices likes drinking and "sabong" (cockfighting) leads to discomfort, other wise discourse worrying about financial strain it brings. Lastly, as a way of coping with the dilemma it has been resolved by silently hoarding resources (money) [Interview Excerpt 5].

This supports the study of (Ohwovoriole, 2022), where having sex is supposed to be enjoyable hence while dealing with melancholy an individual might sob out of the blue during intercourse, indicating problems in relationship. In line with these, the American Addiction Center (2024) affirms that alcohol abuse sabotage, and strain family dynamics, a risk of depleting finances within the family, discourse, and worse harm.

Love in the Reflection of Two People

This theme revealed that marriage can be driven by "awa" (pity) rather than love. First, the respondent highlighted that affection developed over time, driven by words of affirmation. Secondly, as united by vows, it is shown that unconditional love lies within the willingness to stay, support, give love and care, these proves that marriage is not just built by love but as well as emotional support, and value of communication. Lastly, it described that even in the midst of uncertainties, an individual can open their heart through compassion, and acceptance that foster a strong relationship [Interview Excerpt 6].

In connection, Cristian (2023) explained the importance of words of affirmation to let their partner know that they are valued, respected, and loved. Thus, Rathor (2023) expresses when an individual knows that they have someone who loves them and will assist them in times of need, having a supportive partner can help lower stress and anxiety levels thus make a relationship better.

Envisioning Future with Clear Sight

This theme suggests that hope for future rooted from both past and present efforts. First, a brighter future is envisioned through their collaborative effort, and hard work as partners, aimed to establish stability and security for them and their children's education and their whispers of desires for the family's future are imbued with prayers that echoes with fear, and hope for partner to continue an ability to see. Lastly, envisioning themselves renewing their vows with God's blessing for fifty-year union [Interview Excerpt 7].

In accordance, Cavanagh & Fomby (2019) presented that development and promotion of children's wellbeing is one of the fundamental roles of family including the family's ability to provide resources, and emotional support. Hence, Api (2023) explained the history of celebrating golden anniversaries where expected especially to receive a gold wreath (50 years).

Valuable Lessons From Life Experiences

The final theme ventures the moral. First, respondents expressed nostalgia for teenage years and a regret for not completing education, imagining how different their lives might be. Secondly, regret is an inevitable experience, they learned the importance of controlling temper, influenced by religious beliefs. Lastly, it is shown that love involves continually giving and receiving support, and compassion. These lessons signifies that genuine love roots from compassion, and acceptance, sustaining their marriage through all circumstances, till death do them apart [Interview Excerpt 8].

Based on the theme, this linked to Segal et. al (2015) study, found that individuals wedded underage experience psychosocial repercussions and inability to complete education is not hindered by poverty rather early marriage. Additionally, Bosio (2022) stated that couples must have patience to comprehend each parties and respect individual. Thus, Pace (2023) affirmed that it's important for couples to show affection (love, and support) to create a stable, enduring, and healthy connection.

Conclusions

From the significant findings discussed above, the researchers conclude that;

Visual impairment continues to strike as a pressing health issue in the Province of Batangas, this prompts a broader concern across the country, the Philippines, implying a need of attention and intervention as this study shows that the life of individuals while wedded to a visually impaired partners is emotionally taxing, from surviving in the brink of poverty to complexities of marital relationships including the experiences of being shrouded with fog of criticisms, and disapprovals, exhaustions from discourse within partner's vices and visual impairment.

Vulnerability as an individual wedded to a visually impaired partner is inexorable. The life experiences of these individuals somber a truth of having internal struggles such having pity with their partner with visual impairment. This study illustrates that their journey is a transformative path, where it began with compassion, acceptance, and love that serves as essential elements in sustaining their marriage relationships. A balance of giving, and receiving support is a testament of mutual dependence simply by having patience, temper control, and faith.

Additionally, “Hindi Bulag Ang Puso” gives us the idea that the heart truly does not spare anyone for wanting a partner for a lifetime. Visual impairment of a partner implicates challenges, and its share of doubts for an individual’s capability to love and to be loved and it takes courage to choose someone with this condition. Furthermore, it can be noted their partners may not see with their eyes, but their hearts resonates with unconditional love. Because then again, Hindi Bulag Ang Puso (The Heart is not Blind).

Moreover, based on the findings, programs for individuals wedded to visually impaired partners, and the visually impaired themselves can be optical/medical mission that can be organize by the researchers, and volunteers with the help of a strong support system such as Local Government Units (LGUs), a program that can be establish for at least during every quarter to lessen the financial burden of check ups for individuals with visual impairment.

For practice and policy, the Person with Disabilities’ (PWD) Identification card must be utilized to its fullest extent, ensuring the discount in buying medicines. Lastly, as this study reveals that stigmas still persist, fueled by criticisms. Community awareness is needed to alleviate societal pressures faced by individuals wedded to visually impaired partners, and the visually impaired themselves.

Ultimately, the study achieved its goals hence it is not without limitations. First, it is highly recommended to maximize the range of location in finding potential respondents and have a bigger sample. Secondly, as the study is limited to individuals wedded to visually impaired partners, future researcher’s can explore on the domain with having a subject solely visually impaired individuals.

By all means, despite existing studies relating to visual impairment this study serves as an eye opener standing out the experiences of individuals wedded to visually impaired partners that brings forefront of emotional, and social complexities. Thereby, this study contributes to foster inclusivity and supportive environment for all individuals.

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